

2D MoS₂/carbon/polylactic acid filament for 3D printing: Photo and electrochemical energy conversion and storage

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ABSTRACT

Fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D printing has attracted immense attention in the field of energy conversions and storage for rapid prototyping and fabrication of devices in a facile and customized way. In this study, we fabricated an electrocatalytically active filament for FDM printing comprised of catalytically active material, conductive fillers, and polymer. We explored the different mass loading of conductive fillers (graphite, activated charcoal and multi-walled carbon nanotubes) with respect to the base polymer polylactic acid (PLA) to optimize a filament with good flexibility and conductivity. To obtain the

(photo)electrocatalytically active filament, an active material was added into the optimized carbon/polymer filament to fabricate the 3D-printed electrodes. We selected MoS₂ as an archetypal 2D material to demonstrate the functionality of the 3D electrodes in energy conversion and storage applications by the bespoke filament. The 3D-printed MoS₂/carbon electrode shows good (photo)electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction and high capacitive performance. The optimized filament fabrication protocols mitigate the complex fabrication of electrodes by fine-tuning the ratio of polymers and conductive fillers to desired active material such as other 2D materials. This allows the production of many other tunable 3D-printed electrodes for energy conversion and storage and other electrochemical applications.

KEYWORDS: Additive manufacturing, FDM filament fabrication, MoS₂, electrocatalyst, HER, supercapacitor.

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing, commonly known as 3D printing, has gained profound attention in the vast area of applications including aircraft, automobiles, electronics, medical implants, gas, and oil industries because of its rapid prototyping, decentralized manufacturing process, facile fabrication of complex shapes with precision, and minimal manufacturing waste [1-4]. Among various 3D printing techniques, the fused deposition modeling (FDM) technique has become widely popular because of its inexpensive and simplistic fabrication process. In FDM, a filament is employed to print the desired 3D shape [5]. The filament is commonly made of thermoplastic polymers such as polylactic acid (PLA), acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG), and polycarbonate (PC) [6,7]. However, these thermoplastic polymers are non-conductive and do not serve the prerequisite of electrochemical applications.

Several research groups came forward to fabricate conductive filaments by incorporating graphene as conductive fillers with ABS and PLA polymers [8-12]. Electrochemistry research

using 3D printed conductive electrodes had grown exponentially since commercial conductive graphene/PLA filaments became available [13-15]. Moreover, post-modification of the 3D electrodes by electrochemical deposition, dip coating, and atomic layer deposition (ALD) to coat polypropylene (PPy), transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), transition metal carbides or nitrides (MXene) opens new opportunities in vast electrochemical applications [14,16-19]. At the core, the commercial filament contains only ≈ 10 wt% of carbon and ≈ 90 wt% of PLA with trace amount of additives such as TiO_2 and Fe_3O_4 [13,20]. The inherent impurities often dramatically influence the electrochemical properties [21,22], which might not be desirable for certain applications. Additionally, long activation time is required to remove the large quantity of insulating PLA from the 3D-printed electrode to increase their electrochemical activities [23-26]. All these post-3D printing processing consist of several steps which are often painstaking. To avoid such complex post-treatment procedures, the filament fabrication research has resumed with the aim to load high amount of conductive fillers and electroactive 2D nanomaterials into the FDM filament for 3D printing. For the suitable cathodes and anodes in Li-ion battery application, Reyes et al. [27] and Maurel et al. [28] fabricated Li-based filaments through loading of lithium manganese oxide (LMO), lithium titanium oxide (LTO), and lithium iron phosphate (LFP) separately into the PLA polymer with conductive fillers. In another study, Hughes et al. fabricated MoSe_2 /carbon filament for electrocatalytic water splitting [29]. To further expand the FDM 3D printing in electrochemical applications, our aim is to fabricate an electro- and photocatalytic active filament for energy conversion and storage through high mass loading of conductive fillers and active 2D materials.

To obtain a clean and economical energy source, hydrogen production was found to be an alternative resource. One of the most promising and eco-friendly approaches for hydrogen production is photo- and electrochemical water splitting. As a substitution of platinum with relatively inexpensive and abundant catalyst, 2D nanomaterials such as layered double hydroxides and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) evolved as promising catalyst

materials for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) [30]. TMDs such as MoS₂, WS₂, MoSe₂, WSe₂ show outstanding catalytic activities, and on top of them, MoS₂ has been identified as an exceptional material for HER. The S-Mo-S edge of the 2D MoS₂ layers has been recognized as the active site for HER [31]. Nevertheless, the satisfactory Gibbs free energy for HER with a value close to Pt, along with high exchange current density, an optical bandgap of 1.2–1.9 V and high photoabsorptivity in the visible region conceive MoS₂ as a favorable aspirant for (photo)electrocatalytic HER [32].

Likewise, among other TMDs, MoS₂ has also been recognized as an aspiring material for energy storage application due to its unique structural properties [33,34]. In multilayer MoS₂, the layers are stacked by weak van der Waals force. As the central Mo atoms of the MoS₂ can own a wide range of oxidation states of +2 to +6, MoS₂ demonstrates promising pseudocapacitive behavior [35,36]. With the rise of modern wearable electronics, among the energy storage devices, supercapacitors (SCs) are found to be promising due to their moderate energy density, high power density, long cycle life and safe in use [37-39]. The 3D printing allows facile fabrication and customization of 3D electrodes with desired shape and size for a SC that serves as a power source in complex electronics. Apparently, a 3D electrode possesses higher active surface in the same footprint area. Further, a self-standing 3D electrode eliminates the use of external current collectors such as copper, steel, carbon films or nickel foams [40]. Of-late, many research groups employed the FDM 3D printing techniques to fabricate carbon or graphene based electrodes for SCs [13,14,16,20]. To expedite the versatility of MoS₂ in SCs as well as in photo- and electro- assisted HER, a MoS₂ based catalytically active filament would be advantageous for fabrication of 3D electrodes.

Herein, we fabricated a conductive (photo)electrocatalytically active MoS₂/carbon (C)/PLA filament through extrusion process optimizing the active materials such as activated charcoal (AC), multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), and MoS₂ into the PLA matrix. The resulting filament was loaded by active materials up to 80% by mass ratio to the base

polymer PLA. The localized electrochemical activity of the activated MoS₂/C 3D-printed electrode (3D-PE) was analyzed using scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) to ascertain the active positions of high electrochemical activity. The bespoke MoS₂/C 3D-PE exhibited a noticeable (photo)electrocatalytic HER and excellent capacitive properties. The development of such MoS₂/C/PLA filament for decentralized tabletop manufacturing techniques will allow the expansion into other electrocatalytically active 2D nanomaterials-based filaments for electrochemical energy conversion and storage. Moreover, the work can be diversified to other electrochemical fields beyond (photo)electrochemistry and SCs.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Polyethylene glycol (PEG, M_n 1000), molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂), activated charcoal (AC) DARCO[®]-100 mesh particle size, and potassium nitrate (KNO₃) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany, and the Ferrocene methanol (FcMeOH, 99%) was obtained from abcr, Germany. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) were procured from io.li.tec, Germany. Polylactic acid (PLA, Ingeo biopolymer 2003D) was procured from NatureWorks LLC, USA and the commercial graphene/PLA filament was purchased from Graphene Laboratories Inc., New York, USA. Dichloromethane (DCM) and N, N dimethylformamide (DMF) were purchased from Penta, Czech Republic. The electrolytes were prepared with deionized water with resistivity >18 MΩ cm.

2.2 Fabrication of filament

The filament fabrication process consists of two steps, (i) fabrication of a thick film (≈ 2 mm of thickness) and (ii) extrusion of small pieces of film as a filament. In step (i), to prepare the film, at first, the base polymer PLA was dissolved in DCM in a ratio of 0.1 g mL⁻¹ with continuous stirring in a beaker for 2-3 hours until a clear solution was obtained. The beaker

was sealed tightly to prevent the evaporation of DCM at room temperature. Next, PEG which acts as plasticizer was added to the polymer solution and continued stirring until it was completely dissolved. The amount of PEG was kept 40% mass ratio to the PLA. Afterward, conductive fillers such as graphite, or both AC and MWCNTs were added and stirred continuously for 1 hour to obtain a homogenized slurry. We fabricated five different films followed by filaments varying the conductive fillers content from lower to higher amount trading the percolation limit of conductivity and flexibility of the film. The mass ratio of the PLA, PEG and conductive fillers are listed in Table 1. After optimizing the conductive fillers (AC + MWCNTs), to obtain a catalytically active filament, MoS₂ was added in the slurry to partially replace the AC. The slurry was poured onto large glass petri-dishes and kept for 12 hours to evaporate the solvent at room temperature. The amount of slurry poured onto the petri-dishes keeping in mind to reach a film thickness of ~2 mm. The casted films were peeled off from the petri-dishes and cut into small pieces of $\sim 4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$ for extrusion purpose. In step (ii), the small pieces of films ($\sim 4 \times 4 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$) were fed into a filament extruder (Felfil Evo, Italy). The extrusion temperature was kept at 175-177 °C with the screw rpm of 8-9. The filament was wound in a spool attached to the extruder set up. The diameter of the filament was controlled to 1.7 mm controlling the screw rpm and spool pulling speed. To realize a successful filament extrusion, 35-40 g of total batch weight was considered for the extrusion process. Varying the compositions of the ingredients of the films as stated above, five different filaments were fabricated to understand their printing behavior, conductivity, and performances of the printed electrodes towards energy conversion, which are described in the following section.

2.3 3D printing of electrodes

To carry out the 3D printing, the electrodes were designed using Fusion 360 software, and the *.stl* drawing file was sliced using Prusa slicer software to obtain a *gcode* file for 3D

printing. The printing was carried out using the 3D printer (Prusa i3 MK3, Czech Republic) maintaining a nozzle temperature of 220 °C and a bed temperature of 60 °C employing the as-prepared filaments. To remove the excess PLA layer on the electrode surface, the 3D-printed electrodes (3D-PEs) were activated through immersing in DMF for 1 minute followed by washing with ethanol and water several times, and dried in an electric oven at 65 °C for 3 hours. The activated electrodes were used for subsequent studies.

2.4 Materials characterization

The scanning electron microscope (SEM, FEI VERIOS 460L) was used to characterize the surface morphology of the conductive fillers and 3D-PEs. The energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy was carried out for elemental mapping of the constituent components in the 3D-printed electrode using the EDX detector (EDAX SDD Octane Super) attached along with the SEM. Moreover, the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Kratos AXIS Supra) was carried out with a monochromatic Al K α (1486.7 eV) excitation source to determine the chemical composition and bonding environment of the MoS₂. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was carried out using Rigaku SmartLab 3 kW X-ray diffractometer following Bragg Brentano geometry using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm) operating at a voltage of 40 kV and a current of 30 mA. To measure the electrical resistivity of the 3D-PEs, a 4-probe station (Cascade Microtech MPS 150) connected to a source measure unit (SMU, Keithley 4200-SCS Parameter Analyzer), controlled by Clarius software was employed. The van der Pauw sheet resistance measurement was carried out by applying a current of 1 mA.

2.5 Electrochemical characterization

The surface activity was measured by a scanning electrochemical microscope (SECM, Sensolytics, Germany) in a three-electrode setup with graphite as counter and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) as the reference electrode. The ultra-microelectrode (UME) was a commercially available 25 μ m diameter Pt disk UME (Sensolytics, Germany). The probe approach curves

(PACs) were measured in feedback mode with $E_{\text{UME}} = 0.4 \text{ V}$, $1 \mu\text{m}$ step width and $1 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ approach speed until a contact between tip and substrate was observed. The calculation of the approach curves was done according to the literature [41]. Before SECM imaging, the UME was approached using the feedback mode until contact was observed and subsequently retrieved to a substrate-to-tip distance of $\approx 28 \mu\text{m}$. SECM imaging in feedback mode with biased substrate was done in redox mediator solution (1.5 mM FcMeOH in 0.2 M KNO_3) with the applied potentials of $E_{\text{UME}} = 0.4 \text{ V}$ and $E_{\text{substrate}} = 0 \text{ V}$ and a pixel size of $20 \mu\text{m}$. The imaging of the HER was done in substrate generation/tip collection (SG/TC) mode in $1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ with $E_{\text{substrate}} = -1.2 \text{ V}$, $E_{\text{UME}} = 0.3 \text{ V}$ and a pixel size of $12.5 \mu\text{m}$. The SECM images were recorded from constant height with a maximum scan speed of $300 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and a waiting time of 4 ms . The data were processed with the Gwyddion 2.55 software.

The (photo)electrochemical analysis for HER was carried out via linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) technique in three-electrode test system using Ag/AgCl (1 M KCl) as reference and graphite as the counter electrode in $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ at the scan of 2 mV s^{-1} employing a potentiostat PGSTAT 204 (Metrohm Autolab, Netherlands) equipped with Nova 2.1 software. The low scan rate was selected to minimize the additional current contribution to the electrocatalytic HER process from the capacitive charging [42]. The light source employed for (photo)electrochemical experiment as a customized setup consisting of light-emitting diodes (LED, LZ4-44UV00, LZ4-40B208, LZ4-40G108, and LZ4-40R208, LedEngin Inc.) with the wavelengths centered at 365, 460, 523 and 660 nm, respectively. The potentials using Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode were converted against reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) following literature [43]. All (photo)electrochemical experiments including LSV, and SECM imaging were carried out under quiescent electrolyte conditions. The capacitance analyses were carried out using cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) following the similar three-electrode test system with Pt as counter electrode using the same potentiostat.

The EIS study was carried out in the frequency range from 100 Hz to 0.01 Hz by applying an alternating current of 10 mV.

The areal capacitance (C_a) of the electrode was calculated from the CV study using Eq. 1:

$$C_a = \frac{\int_{V_1}^{V_2} I(V) dV}{v (V_2 - V_1) A} \quad (1)$$

where, $I(V)$ is the cathodic current of the CV loop, v is the scan rate, A is the active area of the electrode, and V_1 and V_2 are the potential limits in the CV study. Moreover, the C_a of the electrode was also calculated from the constant current discharging curve of GCD study using Eq. 2:

$$C_a = \frac{I \times \Delta t}{\Delta V \times A} \quad (2)$$

where, I is the constant discharge current, Δt is the total discharging time and ΔV is the discharge voltage range. To calculate gravimetric capacitance, the active area (A) in denominator is replaced by active mass (m) of the electrode [44,45].

3. Results and discussion

In this study, we systematically developed five different filaments varying the compositions of the constituent fillers aiming to obtain a good balance between printability and conductivity. The filament was prepared in two steps, in step (i) a film about ~2 mm of thickness was casted, and in step (ii) small pieces of the film were fed into an extruder to fabricate the filament. The filament fabrication process is depicted by a schematic diagram in Fig. 1a. The composition of filaments, printing behavior and conductivity of the as-printed electrodes are stated in Table 1. At first, we fabricated the filament by loading graphite powders as conductive fillers. It is noteworthy to mention here that, for all filaments, the mass ratio of base polymer (PLA) to plasticizer polyethylene glycol (PEG) was kept at 100:40. For filament-1, the mass ratio of graphite to PLA was 50:100, which yielded an excessively flexible filament that was not printable. For

filament-2, the graphite content was increased to reduce the flexibility, i.e. mass ratio of graphite to PLA was 100:100. The filament with a good balance of mechanical stability and flexibility was then printed smoothly by the 3D-printer. The 3D-printed electrode shows a high sheet resistivity of 7024 Ω/sq . For comparison, an electrode printed from the commercial graphene/PLA filament [46] shows a sheet resistivity of 9330 Ω/sq , which elucidates that with the above mass loading of graphite provides a

Fig. 1. Schematic of (a) filament fabrication, (b) 3D printing, and applications of 3D-printed electrodes in (photo)electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction and in a supercapacitor.

slightly better conductive filament than commercial filament. To further improve the conductivity of the electrode for electrochemical applications, for the next batch (filament-3), the graphite powder was completely replaced by the equivalent amount of activated charcoal (AC) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The mass ratio of AC to MWCNTs to PLA was kept 90:10:100. However, the resulting filament is very brittle, which neither can be rolled in a spool nor can be printed. It should be highlighted that the same amount of fillers in filament-2 (graphite) and in filament-3 (AC+MWCNTs), do not result in the same printability. This is because the graphite

powder offers lubricating effect [47,48] whereas AC and MWCNTs do not possess such properties. Thus, to revert to a flexible filament that is suitable for 3D printing, the mass loading of fillers (AC+MWCNTs) was decreased. In filament-4, the AC to MWCNTs to PLA ratio was kept 70:10:100. The obtained filament showed an optimized flexibility and printability. The 3D-printed electrode from the filament-4 recorded a sheet resistivity of 2641 Ω/sq which is ~ 2.6 times lower than the electrode printed from pure graphite-based filament (filament-1).

Table 1. Summary of filament composition and their general properties.

Filaments	Composition (wt%)	Mass ratio	General properties and printability	Sheet resistivity (Ω/sq) of 3D-printed electrodes
Filament-1 Graphite/PLA/PEG	26.3/52.6/21.0	50:100:40	Not printable, extensively flexible	NA ^[a]
Filament-2 graphite/PLA/PEG	41.7/41.7/16.6	100:100:40	Good printability	7024
Filament-3 AC/MWCNTs/PLA/PEG	37.5/4.2/41.7/16.6	90:10:100:40	Very brittle, not printable	NA
Filament-4 AC/MWCNTs/PLA/PEG	31.8/4.5/45.5/18.2	70:10:100:40	Moderate flexible, good printability	2641
Filament-5 AC/MWCNTs/MoS ₂ /PLA/PEG	22.7/4.5/9.0/45.5/18.2	50:10:20:100:40	Good printability	528
Commercial filament [46] Graphene/PLA	8/92 ^[9]	-	Good printability	9330

[a] NA = not applicable

As a satisfactory printability and conductivity filament is now achieved, we incorporate MoS₂ in the filament (filament-5) by replacing 20% of the AC by MoS₂

and maintaining the ratio of total fillers to PLA 80:100, following the optimized recipe of filament-4. The filament-5 retains the good printing behavior, and the printed electrode displays a sheet resistivity of 528 Ω/sq . In principle, higher amount of MoS_2 can be loaded in the filament, however, the flexibility and printability of the filaments are compromised. We followed the common post-printing treatment on 3D-printed electrode, i.e. partial removal of PLA, [16,21] through immersing in DMF for 1 minute for ‘activation’. After the removal of surface PLA, the activated electrode from filament-5 showed a low sheet resistivity of 11 Ω/sq . The as-printed electrodes from filament-2, -4 and -5 are labeled as graphite/PLA, (AC+MWCNTs)/PLA and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{C}/\text{PLA}$ 3D-PEs and after activation they are denoted as graphite, AC+MWCNT, and MoS_2/C 3D-PEs, respectively for the subsequent discussion.

Prior to electrochemical analyses, we carried out conventional material characterizations for all conductive fillers and 3D-PEs. The surface morphology of pristine AC, MWCNTs, MoS_2 , and MoS_2/C 3D-PEs before and after activation were imaged by SEM. Fig. 2a depicts the SEM image of AC which shows large flakes with a width of $\sim 5\text{-}7\ \mu\text{m}$ and $1\text{-}2\ \mu\text{m}$ of thickness. Fig. 2b displays the SEM image of MWCNTs with diameters of 50-80 nm and lengths of few microns. Fig. 2c depicts the SEM image of MoS_2 which appeared as random shaped flakes with size of about $1\text{-}2\ \mu\text{m}$. The morphology of the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{C}/\text{PLA}$ 3D-PE (as-printed electrode from filament-5) is shown in Fig. 2d, where the constituent fillers are not clearly visible. Apparently, the AC, MWCNTs and MoS_2 are masked by the layer of PLA. However, the fillers are observable after the activation in DMF as depicted in Fig. 2e. This is because, the solvent DMF aids to remove the insulating PLA layers from the surface of the electrode. A magnified image of the MoS_2/C 3D-PE (activated electrode) is shown in Fig. 2f which shows that the MWCNTs knotted the MoS_2 and AC particles. The optical photographs of the MoS_2/C 3D-PEs before and after activation are shown as inset in

Fig. 2d and e, respectively. The electrode retains the shape after the solvent activation. Actually, the presence of MWCNTs in the filament benefits in dual ways, firstly, it increases the conductivity of the electrode, and, secondly, it binds the MoS₂ and AC particles in the activated electrode.

Fig. 2. Scanning electron microscopy images (a) activated charcoal (AC), (b) multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (c) MoS₂ (d) MoS₂/C/PLA 3D-PE, inset: optical photograph; MoS₂/C 3D-PE (e) at low-magnification, inset: optical photograph and (f) high-magnification; energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (g) mapping area, (h) overlay of elements, and mapping of (i) Mo, (j) S, and (k) C of MoS₂/C 3D-PE.

The SEM-EDX mapping was carried out for the MoS₂/C 3D-PE to find out the distribution of MoS₂ and C particles in the electrode matrix. Fig. 2h-k show the overlay of all elements, and individual elemental mapping of Mo, S, and C, respectively. The maps illustrate that the MoS₂ particles are well-dispersed in the electrode matrix.

To understand the crystalline structures of the MoS₂, XRD analysis was carried out from 10 to 80° as depicted in Fig. 3a. All the diffraction peaks correspond to 2H MoS₂

of hexagonal crystal system as per ICDD no. 37-1492. The sharp and high intense peak at 14.4° is assigned to (002) plane with a d-spacing of 6.155 \AA [49].

Fig. 3. (a) X-ray diffraction study of pristine MoS₂. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (b) survey spectra, deconvolution of (c) Mo 3d and (d) S 2p, (e) C 1s and (f) O 1s of MoS₂/C 3D-PE.

The XPS study was carried out for both as-printed and activated MoS₂/C 3D-PE electrodes as shown in Fig. 3b. The survey spectrum of the as-printed electrode shows only the presence of O 1s and C 1s peaks at 532 and 285 eV, respectively, whereas, the activated electrode shows the additional peaks at 229 and 162 eV corresponding to Mo 3d and S 2p peaks, respectively, along with C 1s and O 1s peaks. This proves that the PLA layer on the surface of the as-printed electrode is removed after activation and the active materials are exposed at the electrode's surface. The deconvolution of high-resolution core-level spectrum of Mo 3d (Fig. 3c) shows two prominent peaks at 229.78 and 232.93 eV corresponding to the Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{5/2} and Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{3/2} states,

respectively [50]. The peak located at 226.94 eV corresponds to the S 2s. The deconvolution of the S 2p spectrum (Fig. 3d) shows two high intense peaks at 162.63 and 163.79 eV corresponding to the $S^{2-} 2p_{3/2}$ and $S^{2-} 2p_{1/2}$ states acquainting a spin-orbit peak separation of 1.16 eV [50]. Thus, it can be concluded that the MoS_2 phase is unchanged after the filament extrusion. The deconvolution of C 1s (Fig. 3e) shows the peaks at 284.1, 284.8, 286.3 and 288.6 eV corresponding to the C=C (sp^2), C-C (sp^3), C-O and C=O bonds, respectively [51], which are originated from the remaining PLA, MWCNTs and AC. Further, the deconvolution of O 1s peak (Fig. 3f) shows the presence of C=O, C-O and O-C=O peaks which are well-matched with C 1s peaks [51].

Besides, the non-invasive mapping of topographic details and the electrochemical activity with a high spatial resolution of the MoS_2/C 3D-PE was carried out using SECM technique [52,53]. The SECM was operated amperometrically in feedback and generation/collection modes. In feedback mode, the detected signal is influenced by the distance and the conductivity of the surface. For an insulating surface, like glass and PLA, the diffusion of the redox-active species towards the ultra-microelectrode (UME) is impeded, resulting in a decrease of the current (negative feedback). For conductive surfaces, like carbon and transition metal chalcogenides, the current increases due to the formation of a redox cycle (positive feedback) [54,55].

Fig. 4. Scanning electrochemical microscopic characterization (a) probe approach curves at different positions of the MoS_2/C 3D-PE, (b) SECM imaging in feedback

mode with biased substrate and (c) substrate generation/tip collection mode image for the hydrogen evolution in 1 M H₂SO₄ at $E_{\text{substrate}} = -1.2$ V with $E_{\text{UME}} = 0.3$ V (vs. Ag/AgCl, 3 M KCl) of the MoS₂/C 3D-PE.

The ideal positive and negative feedback (black line) are marked in probe approach curves (PACs) in Fig. 4a. The feedback curve (red lines) recorded at different spots of MoS₂/C 3D-PE are between both ideal curves, which implies that the surface conductivity is heterogeneous. The SECM image in Fig. 4b is collected using the feedback mode with biased substrate. The image shows an uneven morphology of the MoS₂/C 3D-PE with locally high currents due to the enhanced signal of the recycling of the redox mediator on the conductive components.

For the characterization of the electrochemical activity, SECM imaging was applied in the generation/collection mode. In this mode, the electrochemical activity is directly probed by the detection of the hydrogen evolution and the mapped image is shown in Fig. 4c. The hydrogen produced at the MoS₂/C 3D-PE was detected via its oxidation at the UME. A highly local HER activity generates greater signals (red spots). Such HER hot-spots point to the partial coverage of the catalyst material on the electrode surface. In both SECM modes the electrode surface was found to be conductive and active which confirm the uniform distribution of the conductive fillers. Furthermore, the SECM enabled the localization of highly active MoS₂ on the 3D-PE surface.

Fig. 5a presents the LSV curves for HER in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte. We first compare the HER for 3D-PEs from the filament-2, 4, 5 and the commercial filament with similar activation procedures. Our fabricated graphite 3D-PE (from filament-2) is slightly better than the 3D-PE from the commercial filament, however, both are far from being practical to catalyze the HER. With the addition of MoS₂ as a catalyst to the AC+MWCNT filament of filament-4, the resulting MoS₂/C 3D-PE (from filament-

5) presents a remarkable electrocatalytic improvement with much reduced overpotential. As MoS₂ is a photo-active semiconductor, we evaluate the possibility of photo-assisted HER by irradiating the reaction with light sources of different wavelengths, spanning from the UV to the visible spectral region and the corresponding LSV curves are depicted in Fig. 5b. Clearly, a significant reduction of overpotential is observed by the irradiation with the UV light source. The overpotential is further reduced with the gradual increment of wavelengths from the blue to red region, indicating that MoS₂ is more responsive in the visible spectral region [19]. The overpotentials at the common comparison point at -10 mA cm^{-2} are presented in Fig. 5c. An obvious reducing trend is observed as discussed above. Specifically, the irradiation by UV light source has decreased the overpotential from ≈ 823 to ≈ 623 mV, and finally to ≈ 449 mV by red wavelength light (660 nm) source, which is nearly half of the overpotential recorded without irradiation.

To verify the photoresponses of the MoS₂/C 3D-PE, we applied a constant potential (V_{RHE}) of -0.45 V (vs. reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE)) selected from the LSV curves in Fig. 5a in the same electrolyte. The corresponding change of the current density-time profile is shown in Fig. 5d. With continuous switching between the on and off states of the irradiation sources, the MoS₂/C 3D-PE responded accordingly with a consistent response over six on/off cycles. In particular, the largest change of current density is observed by the irradiation of the red wavelength light source, which agrees with the lowest overpotential in Fig. 5c. These results concretely show that the HER is both electro- and further photo-catalyzed by MoS₂/C 3D-PE to achieve a more efficient energy conversion purpose, utilizing MoS₂ as a catalytically active material in the filament to harvest the abundant energy across the solar spectrum. It is important to mention here that the acidic electrolyte promotes the reduction of protons on the catalyst surface, where H_3O^+ is reduced to H_2 and H_2O through multiple-step mechanisms (Volmer,

Heyrovsky, Tafel steps reported in the literature) [56]. Thus, along with the progress of HER, the concentration of H_3O^+ ions decreased.

Fig. 5. Characterization of the (photo)electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte. (a) Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves of 3D-printed blank carbon-based electrodes and MoS₂/C electrode with a 3D-printed electrode from commercial carbon filament as a reference, (b) LSV curves without and with irradiation by different light sources, $\lambda = 365, 460, 523,$ and 660 nm of MoS₂/C 3D-PE, LSV scan rates: 2 mV s^{-1} (c) HER overpotentials of MoS₂/C 3D-PE at -10 mA cm^{-2} , (d) photo-responses with continuous light on and off of MoS₂/C 3D-PEs irradiated by different light sources, applied potential $V_{\text{RHE}} = -0.45 \text{ V}$.

Table 2 compares the (photo)electrocatalytic performance of the MoS₂/C 3D-PE with MoS₂ deposited on 3D-printed carbon electrode. Our 3D electrodes produced by MoS₂/carbon based filament shows a comparable overpotentials with respect to other electrodes that required a separate MoS₂ deposition process.

Table 2. Comparison of (photo)electrocatalytic activities of MoS₂/carbon 3D-printed electrodes. In all studies, 0.5 M H₂SO₄ was used as electrolyte.

Electrode	Fabrication technique	Overpotential (mV) vs. RHE at -10 mA cm^{-2}	Ref.
MoS ₂ coated 3D carbon electrode	Spray-coating of MoS ₂	≈ 550	[57]
MoS ₂ coated 3D carbon electrode	Electrodeposition of MoS ₂	≈ 390	[55]
MoS ₂ coated 3D carbon electrode	Atomic layer deposition of MoS ₂	≈ 490 ≈ 440 (illumination)	[19]
MoS ₂ /carbon 3D electrode	Extrusion of MoS ₂ , carbon and PLA	≈ 820 ≈ 450 (illumination)	This work

In the next step, our MoS₂/C 3D-PE was employed to study the capacitive performance for the potential use in an energy storage device. The CV was studied in a three-electrode test system in 1 M H₂SO₄ to understand the kinetics of the MoS₂/C 3D-PE in the potential window of 0–0.8 V with the scan rates of 10 to 100 mV s⁻¹ as shown in Fig. 6a. The current density was increased with increasing scan rates, and the CV pattern appeared as quasi-rectangular shape and maintained a similar shape at higher scan rates which indicate fast and reversible surface-controlled capacitive behavior. The MoS₂/C 3D-PE shows an areal capacitance (C_a) of 77 mF cm⁻² at the scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. Further, the GCD study was carried out in the same potential window of 0–0.8 V with different current densities as shown in Fig. 6b. The GCD study shows the symmetric charge-discharge patterns with a triangular shape which

apparently corroborates the surface-controlled capacitive behavior as observed in CV study. The MoS₂/C 3D-PE shows a high C_a of 391 mF cm⁻² at the current density of 1.82 mA cm⁻². However, the C_a was decreased with increasing the current densities. The electrode shows the C_a of 306, 235, 204, 125, and 75 mF cm⁻² at the current densities of 2.42, 3, 6, 9, and 12 mA cm⁻², respectively. The decrease of C_a with increasing the current density can be attributed to the faster movement of electrolyte ions during charge-discharge that limits the accessibility of the whole electrochemical

Fig. 6. Characterization for supercapacitor. (a) Cyclic voltammetry study at different scan rates, (b) galvanostatic charge-discharge study at different current densities, (c) electrochemical impedance spectroscopy study: Nyquist plot, inset fitted circuit model, and (d) cyclic stability test using the galvanostatic charge-discharge measurements for 6000 cycles of MoS₂/C 3D-PE in 1 M H₂SO₄, inset: charge-discharge cycles for initial ten cycles.

active surface area. Besides, the gravimetric capacitance was found to be 19 F g^{-1} at the specific current of 85.7 mA g^{-1} . The numeric gravimetric capacitance value apparently appeared lower; however, it is noteworthy to be mentioned here that the 3D-printed MoS₂-C electrode acts as free-standing electrode without any external current collectors (such as nickel foam, carbon cloth, copper foil, and steel film) unlike other SC devices. Thus, the electrode containing of carbon materials, MoS₂ and remaining PLA (that provides mechanical strength of the electrode) resulted a mass loading of 21.23 mg cm^{-2} providing specific capacitance of 19 F g^{-1} at the specific current of 85.7 mA g^{-1} .

Moreover, to evaluate the impedance behavior of the MoS₂/C 3D-PE, the Nyquist plot from the EIS study and the fitted plot by corresponding equivalent circuit model are shown in Fig. 6c. The circuit model consists of an equivalent series resistance (R_s), charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}), constant phase element (CPE) and Warburg resistance (W_d). The R_s represents the equivalent series resistance which includes the intrinsic resistance of the electrode material, interfacial resistance between the electrode material and current collector, and the interfacial resistance between electrode material and electrolyte [58]. The R_s is determined from the intersection point of the Nyquist plot at x -axis in the high frequency which was found to be $9.46 \text{ } \Omega$. The MoS₂/C 3D-PE possesses some inherent resistance due to the presence of insulating PLA in the bulk of the electrode. The R_{ct} is determined from the diameter of the semicircle of the Nyquist plot at the high-frequency region. The R_{ct} was found to be $25.4 \text{ m}\Omega$. The low R_{ct} value can be ascribed to the conductive surface offered by AC and MoS₂ that facilitate faster charge transfer from the bulk of electrolyte to the electrode's surface. The C_{dl} was found to be 144 mF . The slope of the straight line at the post semicircle region measures the W_d . The inclined line presents a real supercapacitor behavior where charge storage is controlled by surface-controlled

electrochemical double-layer (EDL) and pseudocapacitive mechanisms. The W_d was found to be $29.5 \text{ mS s}^{0.5}$. The *CPE* explains the deviation of a real SC from an ideal condition. The impedance (Z) is related to *CPE* (Y_0) by the Eq. 3 [59]:

$$Z = (Y_0 j \omega)^{-n} \quad (3)$$

where ω is the angular frequency. The power factor n deviates as $0 < n < 1$. The n value closer to 1 specifies ideal EDL capacitor. The *CPE* was found to be $166 \mu\text{S s}^n$, where $n = 0.738$. The n value suggests that the charge storage mechanism is dominated by EDL-type capacitive behavior.

Further, the cyclic stability of the MoS_2/C 3D-PE was studied by measuring the GCD for 6000 cycles at the current density of 7 mA cm^{-2} . The electrode showed excellent cyclic stability where the capacitance slightly increased until 800 cycles and then gradually decreased and maintained $\sim 99\%$ of the initial capacitance until 5000 cycles. The capacitance was further decayed to 92% after 6000 cycles. The initial ten cycles of GCD data are displayed as an inset in Fig. 6d. The initial increment of capacitance can be ascribed to the penetrating of the electrolyte ions inside the bulk of the electrode in the first few hundred cycles, which facilitates to access more active surface area and consequently increases the capacitance. Subsequently, the active surface area is saturated, and the electrode shows excellent and constant cyclic performance till 5000 cycles. These results show that the free-standing MoS_2/C 3D-PE can be used as a potential electrode in a supercapacitor device. We compared the capacitive performance of the MoS_2/C 3D-PE with other MoS_2 -carbon based electrodes reported in the literature in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of capacitive performance of MoS₂/carbon electrodes.

Electrode	Fabrication technique	Electrolyte	Capacitance	Cyclic stability (capacitance retention)	Ref.
MoS ₂ @CNT	CVD followed by DC sputtering	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	131 mF cm ⁻² at 5 mV s ⁻¹	97.6% after 2500 cycles	[60]
MoS ₂ -graphene	Solution phase exfoliation	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	4.29 mF cm ⁻² at 5 mV s ⁻¹	250% after 10000 cycles	[61]
Carbon-MoS ₂ -carbon nanoplates	Hydrothermal route	1 M Li ₂ SO ₄	0.12 F cm ⁻² at 0.1 A g ⁻¹	85% after 3000 cycles	[62]
MoS ₂ @CNT/rGO	Hydrothermal and vacuum filtration	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	129 mF cm ⁻² at 0.1 mA cm ⁻²	94.7% after 10000 cycles	[63]
MoS ₂ /nanocarbon 3D-printed electrode	Electrodeposition on 3D nanocarbon	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	7.7 mF cm ⁻² at 0.36 mA cm ⁻²	Not provided	[16]
MoS ₂ /rGO/CNT fiber	CVD and hydrothermal	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	131 mF cm ⁻² at 2 A g ⁻¹	90% after 2000 cycles	[64]
MoS ₂ /CNT	Liquid phase exfoliation	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	37 mF cm ⁻² at 20 mV s ⁻¹	95% after 20000 cycles	[65]
MoS ₂ /rGO	Hydrothermal route	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	343 F cm ⁻³ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	98% after 20000 cycles	[66]
MoS ₂ /AC/CNT 3D electrode	Filament fabrication	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	391 mF cm ⁻² , at 1.82 mA cm ⁻²	92% after 6000 cycles	This work

It should be taken into account that to successfully extrudate a filament for ~5 m of length, a minimal 35 g of batch size was employed, which contained 27.2 wt% of conductive fillers (9.52 g) and 9 wt% of MoS₂ (3.15 g) (in case of filament-5, as stated in the Experimental section). Therefore, to extrudate a full spool of filament that is comparable to commercial standard, large quantity of MoS₂ will be required. We presented here the fabrication of a prototype MoS₂/C/PLA filament using commercial sources of each material. Considering the size of the MoS₂ flakes, it is noteworthy to mention that the high thickness of MoS₂ causes blocking of the active edge sites and increases electrical resistance which results in slower electron transfer rate, and remarkably influence on electrochemical performance [67,68]. Indeed, the commercial MoS₂ flakes, TMDs or other 2D materials can be exfoliated

with high throughput process for future filament fabrication [69]. It is expected that the exfoliated MoS₂ nanosheets in FDM filament will bring larger impact and better performance for HER and supercapacitor applications in our future study.

4. Conclusions

This study shows that an (photo)electrocatalytically active MoS₂/carbon/polylactic acid (PLA) filament can be fabricated in a facile way trading the conductive fillers such as graphite, activated charcoal (AC), multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), and catalytically active transition metal dichalcogenide MoS₂ for fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D printing. The conductivity, flexibility and printability of the filaments can be tuned varying the mass ratio of the active materials in the base polymer PLA. Remarkably, it was found that the conductive carbon-based fillers (AC and MWCNTs) and MoS₂ can be loaded up to 80% mass ratio to the PLA. The scanning electrochemical microscopy shows the heterogeneity of conductivity over the electrode and catalytically active sites for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The 3D-printed electrode revealed significant photo-activity through the entire visible spectral region, although the highest activity was found at the red wavelength region (660 nm). Moreover, the electrode shows a capacitance of 381 mF cm⁻² at the current density of 1.82 mA cm⁻² and 92% of capacitance retention after 6000 cycles. This study creates a profound impact on filament fabrication for FDM 3D printing because it shows the potential to reveal the other 2D nanomaterials-based filament for other electrochemical applications in the future through tailoring the composition of active materials.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kalyan Ghosh: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition. **Siowwoon Ng:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing –review & editing. **Christian Iffelsberger:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing –review & editing, **Martin Pumera:** Conceptualization, Writing –review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Abbreviations

HER - hydrogen evolution reaction, SC - supercapacitor, 3D-PE - 3D-printed electrode, UME - ultra-microelectrode, PACs - probe approach curves, C_a - areal capacitance, R_s - equivalent series resistance, R_{ct} - charge transfer resistance, C_{dl} - double-layer capacitance, CPE - constant phase element and W_d - Warburg resistance.

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